

Determination of Yield and Yield Components of Fodder Beet (*Beta vulgaris* L. var. *rapacea* Koch.) Cultivars under the Konya Region Conditions

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Abstract : This study was conducted to determination of yield and yield components of some fodder beet types (Amarilla Barres, Feldherr, Kyros, Magnum, and Rota) under the Konya region conditions. Fodder beet was obtained from the Selcuk University, Faculty of Agriculture, at 2006-2007 season and the experiment was established in a randomized complete block design with three replicates. Differences among the averages of the fodder beet cultivars are statistically important in terms of all the characteristics investigated. Leaf attitude value was 1.2-2.2 (1=erect; 5= prostrate), root shape scale value was (1=spheroidal - 9=cylindrical), root diameter 11.0-12.2 cm, remaining part of root on the ground was 6.3-13.7 cm, root length was 21.4 - 29.6 cm, leaf yield 1592 - 1917 kg/da, root yield was 10083-12258 kg/da, root dry matter content was %8.2- 18.6 and root dry matter yield was 889-1887 kg/da. As a result of the study, it was determined that fodder beet cultivars are different conditions in terms of yield and yield components. Therefore, determination of appropriate cultivars for each region affect crop yield importantly.

Keywords : fedder beet, root yield, yield components, Konya, agriculture

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